

**BIOCHEMICAL ANALYSIS OF TURKESTAN SOAP ROOT SAPONS
ALLOCHRUSA GYPSOPHILLOIDES (REGEL) SCHISCHK**

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ABSTRACT

Allochrusa gypsophiloidesis one of the most valuable technical and medicinal plants, officially included into the national pharmacopoeia, andhaving practical applications in many fields of the domestic industry.The aim of this study was a qualitative and quantitative study of saponins from Allochrusa gypsophiloides collected in South Kazakhstan region of the Republic of Kazakhstan. The results of qualitative reactions show the presence of triterpenic saponins in plant material.

Key words: Allochrusa gypsophiloides, triterpenes, saponins, oleanolic acid, hemolytic index, Turkestan soap root, gersabyn, effervescent wines, beer, soft drinks, triterpene saponins, technical saponin, oleanol series.

Introduction. *Allochrusa gypsophiloides* (Regel) Schischk. (*Acanthophyllum gypsophiloides* Rgl., allocruza kachimoforma, thorny cabbage, Turkestan soap root

(TSR), Kazakh. - "gersabyn", English - "turkestan soap root") endemic Central Asian species from the genus *Allochrusa* of the family Caryophyllaceae (*Caryophyllaceae* Juss.).

For many years, TSR has been exported as a valuable source of plant saponins. Industrial harvesting of soap root was carried out on the territory of the republics of Central Asia and the Kazakhstan [1]. Due to the depletion of natural thickets in the Central Asian republics, since the 50th Kazakhstan has been the only supplier of TSR. Annual planned harvesting volumes of dry roots reached 700–800 tons. As a result of many years of intensive and haphazard harvesting, TSR as a rare species with a greatly decreasing number was listed in 1981 in the Red Book of the Kazakhstan.

Objects of investigation. In comparison with similar saponin plants growing in the CIS (soapberry medicinal *Saponaria officinalis*, rocky paniculate *Gypsophila paniculata*, etc.), TSR has an increased level in the roots of triterpene saponins of the oleanol series. Of these, saponins acanthophyllazedides B, C and D are isolated - derivatives of hypsogenin and quilaic acid [2].

The ability of TSR saponins to form a persistent foam with water is used in everyday life (soap, additive to flour for baking lush bread), in the production of shampoos, bath liquids and other detergents. The property of TSR saponins to retain gases is used in the food industry (in the manufacture of halva, creams, whipped cream, effervescent wines, beer, soft drinks), as well as as a foaming component in the production of fire-fighting mixtures. In the 60-80s, technical saponin TSR was used in the manufacture of foam concrete, to improve the technological qualities of concrete, thermal insulation properties and durability of concrete structures, irrigation systems. It should be noted that in recent decades, the use of TSR has been significantly limited due to a sharp decline in the number of species as a result of unsystematic harvesting.

The latest edition of the Red Book of Kazakhstan states as necessary

measures to protect the natural thickets of TSR that "... a licensing fee should be introduced. Limit the annual volume of blanks, monitor the state of renewal, and introduce them more widely into culture". As a result of research conducted since 1999 by the staff of the Institute of Botany and Phytointroduction, it was found that in places that have not been subject to anthropogenic load for a long time (namely overgrazing), natural populations of soap root are restored and selective harvesting can be practiced. To restore and preserve natural populations, it is better to resume the cultivation of Turkestan soap root in culture, which was tested almost half a century ago in Kazakhstan and Uzbekistan. TSR is one of the most valuable medicinal plants of the flora of Kazakhstan, which is included in the official pharmacopoeia. Triterpene saponins TSR are used as expectorants, diuretics, laxatives and tonics, as well as in the composition of oral phytopreparations.

Recent studies have revealed high immunostimulating, antiviral, antitumor activity of TSR extracts, based on the ability of saponins to enhance the immunogenicity of various antigens. Thus, the analysis of the literature indicates that TSR is an economically important organic saponin-bearing plant. The purpose of the study is to study the qualitative composition of TSR saponins and determine their content.

Materials and research methods - for the analysis, plant material of *alochruza kachimovid* was used, collected in the flowering phase - the beginning of fruiting in July 2015 during an expeditionary survey of natural populations of TSR in the territory of the South Kazakhstan region [3-4].

The collected samples of TSR under study were preliminarily subjected to processing and removal of mechanical impurities, as well as drying at ambient temperature and grinding to a certain state in accordance with the requirements of GOST 24027. 1-80. Determination of the moisture content of raw materials and the yield of extractive substances was carried out in accordance with GOST

24027. 2-80. Macroscopic analysis of TSR raw materials was carried out according to GOST 3448-78 Thorn root Specifications [5].

For qualitative analysis, aqueous and alcohol extraction was prepared in a ratio of 1: 10 and the presence of saponin reactions was carried out with them: foaming, hemolytic activity, lead acetate precipitation, Lafon reaction, Salkovsky reaction, etc.

The foaming activity of aqueous extraction was assessed according to a three-point system: 1 point - weak foaming, no more than 15 seconds; 2 point – average foaming. a significant amount of foam is formed, which lasts up to 30 seconds; 3 points - good foaming, the reaction lasts more than 1 minute.

The foam number was determined by the formula $A = 1 / K$, where A is the indicator of the saponin content; K is the lowest concentration of saponin extraction, which forms a foam that does not disappear within 1 minute.

To assess hemolytic activity, extraction on an isotonic solution of sodium chloride 1:10 and insisting on a boiling water bath for 30 minutes was prepared. The solution was cooled and passed through the filter into a measuring flask and its volume was brought to 100 ml. 2 ml of defibrinated blood was added to the 2 ml of extraction. In the presence of saponins, a transparent red solution ("lacquer blood") is formed. In determining the hemolytic index (HI), a number of dilutions of different concentrations were prepared (1: 2000; 1: 1000; 1: 665; 1: 500; 1: 400; 1: 335; 1: 285; 1: 250; 1: 220; 1: 200).

The results of the study - the macroscopic analysis showed that the collected raw materials of TSR roots fully complied with the standard requirements: in appearance, the collected raw materials were heavy, hard, cylindrical pieces of excavated roots, cleaned from the ground and side branches. Mostly spirally twisted with an uneven wrinkled surface covered with a network of numerous small transverse depressions (in the form of thin ring lines), deep longitudinal grooves and cracks, with traces of rounded scars

remaining after the removal of lateral roots [6, 7]. The fracture of the roots is uneven. The color of the roots is light brown on the outside, yellowish on the inside with white veins, the taste is slightly burning, irritating.

The percentage of humidity of the above-ground part of the plant averaged $9.84 \pm 0.14\%$, at the roots $9.00 \pm 2.40\%$. The content of extractive substances in the roots varied depending on the nature of the extractant used and contained: water - $53.31 \pm 2.93\%$; 50% ethanol – $54.20 \pm 1.51\%$; 90% ethanol – $24.38 \pm 0.99\%$. The amount of extractive substances of plants extracted by water and 50% ethyl alcohol do not differ significantly from each other. The results of high-quality reactions with aqueous and alcohol extracts from TSR are presented in table 1.

Table 1

Results of qualitative reactions to the presence of triterpene saponins in the
Turkestan soap root

Qualitative response	Extract (1:10)	Reaction results
Reaction to foaming in acidic and alkaline environments	water	in both test tubes foam, even in volume and durability
Medium lead acetate deposition reaction	alcohol	white sediment in a day
Lafon's reaction	water alcohol	when heated dark green staining, inside a ball-shaped precipitate of white color
Salkovsky's reaction	alcohol	upper phase beige color, bottom layer in yellow-red color
Reaction with alcohol cholesterol solution	alcohol	beige precipitate

The results of the identification of triterpene saponins in TSR by the nature of the staining by the TLC method on Sorbfil plates in various solvent systems before

and after hydrolysis are presented in table 2.

An important property of saponins is the ability to cause the destruction of erythrocytes due to their interaction with the sterols of the erythrocyte membrane, which leads to an increase in their permeability and free release of hemoglobin into the blood plasma and the formation of a red transparent solution "lacquer blood". The quantitative determination of saponins by the hemolytic method is based on the assumption that the hemolytic effect is directly proportional to the amount of substance in the solution. The hemolytic index (HI) is the lowest concentration of extraction from 1 g of raw materials, which causes complete hemolysis of erythrocytes contained in 1 ml of a 2% solution of defibrinated blood.

Table 2

Results of TLC of triterpene saponins in alcohol extraction of TSR before and after hydrolysis

Solvent system	Color of spots and Rf on the chromatogram after manifestation of a 10% solution of sulfuric acid and on heating					
	before hydrolysis		after hydrolysis		oleanolic acid	
Chloroform-ethyl alcohol-water (13:6:1)	-		bluish-purple	0,62	cherry-purple	0,99
			cherry-purple	0,95		
Butanol-acetic acid-water (4:5:1)	dark grey	0,21	bluish-purple	0,66	cherry-purple	0,96
			cherry-purple	0,96		
Chloroform-methanol-water (65:50:10)	dark grey	0,92	cherry-purple	0,95	cherry-purple	0,95
Petroleum ether-chloroform-acetone (20:20:5)	-		cherry-purple	0,2	cherry-purple	0,3

Figure 2 shows the result of a qualitative reaction to the hemolytic activity of the extract of the roots of TSR, prepared on an isotonic solution.

Figure 2. Hemolytic reaction of TSR extract in various dilutions

In the above figure 2, it can be seen that in the test tube with the maximum dilution of the aqueous extract from the roots of the TSR, an almost colorless solution with a precipitate of red bodies at the bottom is observed, which indicates the absence of a hemolysis reaction of erythrocytes. This is followed by a test tube with a red-colored solution, but with a sediment at the bottom (partial hemolysis). In subsequent test tubes, the solution is colored bright red without sediment at the bottom, which indicates the presence of complete destruction of erythrocytes.

Discussion of the results - when conducting a test for the formation of foam characteristic specifically for saponins, it was found that the foam is formed both in the acidic solution of 0.1 n. HCl, and in the alkaline solution of 0.1 n. NaOH, which indicates the presence of triterpene saponins in the studied raw material. When carried out with aqueous and alcohol extracts, Lafon's reactions with concentrated acid, ethanol and 10% iron sulfate solution after heating, blue-green staining and the appearance of a characteristic ball-like precipitate inside the solution were noted. When mixing alcohol extract in chloroform with an equal volume of concentrated sulfuric acid, the upper phase of the solution was colored beige, the lower layer (sulfuric acid) in yellow-red color. When adding an alcohol solution of cholesterol to the alcohol extract, the appearance of a beige precipitate was noted. These qualitative reactions indicate the presence of triterpene saponins in the raw materials of TSR.

The results of qualitative reactions are confirmed by the TLC method in four

different solvent systems. After chromatography of the total alcohol extraction, an unidentified spot appeared in systems 2 and 3 with R_f 0.21. Whereas during the separation of alcohol extraction after hydrolysis in all 4 systems, a spot coincided in cherry-purple color and close in value to the R_f value with the oleanolic acid standard (table 2).

Evaluation of the foaming activity of various parts of the TSR plant showed that the water extract from the above-ground part foams weakly (1b), and from the roots has a good foaming (3 b), which lasted more than 1 min.

The hemolytic activity of the more dilute extract from the roots (initial 1:1000) was significantly higher. Markedly pronounced hemolysis was manifested during the first hour with a final maximum dilution of 1: 6650. A high hemolytic index OF HI 3333 is associated with a higher content of saponins in the roots.

For comparison, hemolytic indices given for other saponin-bearing plants: chestnut seeds – 6000; licorice root – 250–300; soapberry root – 2600– 3900; senega root –2500–4500.

According to various literary sources, the hemolytic index of the Turkestan soap root is 1: 1000 or 1: 2860, and the above-ground part is 1: 240. The results of our own experimental studies revealed a higher hemolytic index of TSR extract collected from natural populations in the South Kazakhstan region at the flowering phase and the beginning of fruiting.

Spectrophotometric quantitative determination of saponins revealed a high content in the roots of 7.63% and almost three times less in the above-ground part, 2.29%. The results of statistical data processing showed that the relative error of determination with a confidence probability of 95% is within the limits, respectively, 4.10% and 8.54%.

Conclusion. Thus, the qualitative and quantitative analysis of saponins of the Turkestan soap root growing on the territory of the South Kazakhstan region

revealed a significant content of triterpene saponins of the oleanol series, which have high surface and hemolytic activity. The data obtained allow us to assert that the creation of a raw material base of *Allochrusa gypsophiloides* in the conditions of the South Kazakhstan region [8-9] is advisable and recommend the species for further introduction as a promising source of triterpene saponins with high biological activity.

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